

Responsible Adoption of Generative AI in Government: Governance, Privacy and Ethical Implications

Alta van der Merwe^[0000-0002-3652-7512A] and Tandile Stuurman

University of Pretoria, Informatics, Pretoria, 0001
alta.vdm@up.ac.za

Abstract. Generative Artificial Intelligence offers governments new ways to improve decision making, strengthen service delivery, and increase operational efficiency. Within the context of Society 5.0, where technology is used to create a human-centred and sustainable society, generative AI plays a key role in integrating digital innovation with social needs. Its ability to generate content, analyze data, and support complex problem solving creates opportunities for more responsive and inclusive public services. At the same time, rapid adoption introduces governance, privacy, and ethical risks. This study examines the responsible adoption of generative AI in government, with a focus on governance frameworks, data privacy, and ethical implications. A qualitative interpretive case study approach was followed. Data were collected through an online questionnaire distributed to members of the Government Information Technology Officer Council. The findings show clear potential for innovation and efficiency, but also highlight risks such as data privacy concerns, algorithmic bias, limited transparency, and weak regulatory structures. The study stresses the need for strong governance, ethical oversight, and stakeholder engagement to ensure generative AI supports the human-centred goals of Society 5.0.

Keywords: Generative Artificial Intelligence, Public Sector Governance, Data Privacy, AI Ethics.

1 Introduction

The evolution of technologies offers opportunities to improve economic efficiency and quality of life; however, they also create many unexpected new risks [1]. There are many opportunities for governments worldwide due to the growing use of AI in government operations [2]. Based on current evidence, artificial intelligence (AI) can improve global productivity growth and positively impact the labour market by fostering human-machine complementarity, substitution, and invention [3]. When AI technologies are incorporated into government procedures and public-sector ecosystems, traditional service delivery, policymaking, and enforcement methods may undergo significant changes [2]. Generative Artificial Intelligence (Gen AI) is a form of AI that aims to use computers to generate models that can interpret and produce new content, such as text, images, music, and videos [4].

This paper aligns with the Society 5.0 perspective by examining how generative artificial intelligence can support a human-centred approach to public sector transformation. Society 5.0 emphasizes the integration of advanced digital technologies with societal needs to improve quality of life, inclusivity, and sustainability. In this context, the study positions generative AI not only as a tool for efficiency and innovation, but as a mechanism to enhance citizen-focused service delivery and informed decision making. By addressing governance, privacy, and ethical considerations, the paper contributes to ongoing discussions on how governments can adopt emerging technologies in a responsible manner that balances technological progress with social value.

2 Background

Since the end of apartheid in 1994, the South African public service has undergone significant change. The post-apartheid government aimed to create a democratic and inclusive public service, marking a stable shift from the authority of the apartheid era. This process involved a comprehensive reorganization of the country's institutions, with the public service playing a key role in the transformation, designed to improve government responsiveness to the needs of all South Africans [5]. South Africa is at a critical juncture in its digital transformation, presenting an opportunity to implement a coordinated, delivery-focused strategy for leveraging technology to enhance service delivery, stimulate economic growth, and promote an inclusive society [6]. The digitization of public administration is vital for modernizing government systems. It involves deploying advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things, sensor networks, big data analytics, and artificial intelligence (AI) [2].

AI systems in public services appear to have the potential to expand the public sector's capabilities in several areas, and the public sector is increasingly utilizing these systems [7]. Service delivery has been impacted by Generative AI [8]; models such as ChatGPT foster collaboration by enhancing human-machine communication and co-creativity [9]. The chatbot industry is one of the areas in which artificial intelligence (AI) has attracted much attention. ChatGPT was launched in 2018 by OpenAI. Workplace tasks are influenced by Generative AI technologies [10]. It provides tailored information, stimulates creativity, and improves digital skills, enhancing learning [11]. In various industries Artificial Intelligence is quickly transitioning from experimentation to practical use [12]. The rapid development of generative AI technologies has sparked discussions about the benefits, limitations, and risks associated with the increasing capabilities of artificial intelligence [13]. The sensitive information generated by generative AI might lead to a potential data privacy breach. Legal frameworks, which offer norms, regulations, and channels for responsibility and redress, are essential for regulating AI development and application [14].

Ethical concerns are emerging since AI systems are becoming increasingly common daily and drive innovation in various industries [15]. Concerns have been raised by consumers and privacy advocates about the challenges associated with the commercial use of AI [12]. Government regulation is still developing, and dangers are

associated with the unrestricted use of AI [16]. The deployment of Generative AI involves managing vast datasets, which introduces critical concerns about privacy and security [17]. Ethics is a highly debated topic with diverse viewpoints and perspectives despite the success and potential of AI applications [18]. The authors, Rousi et. al [19] advise that businesses must carefully evaluate ethical risks and take action to mitigate them when deploying generative AI systems. Understanding the moral complexities of AI technology and its uses can be facilitated by applying ethical principles in a structured manner [20]. Generative AI technologies have a wide-reaching impact and the potential to reshape social, political, and economic structures in the 21st century [16].

Generative AI presents severe concerns through the tool's accessibility [21]. There is a potential high risk of misuse in generative AI for the data subjects [11]. These risks can lead to new types of criminal activity, such as AI fraud, defamation, identity theft, and impersonation [22]. Consumer's private information should always be protected when using generative AI technology, which is essential because it could cause harm if disclosed [18]. More efforts are needed to create robust frameworks and ethical standards to ensure responsible deployment and increase accuracy and efficiency [13].

Despite studies on generative AI, an extensive literature review revealed a limited body of research on ethical, privacy, and governance issues related to generative AI, particularly within the South African government. In response to this issue, the study evaluated the ethical, privacy, and governance concerns associated with deploying generative artificial intelligence. Although the South African government has acknowledged AI's potential to improve services, there are no guidelines for deploying generative AI in public service.

3 Research Methodology

The main research question that guided the study was: *How can the public service address the governance, privacy and ethics concerns to ensure their generative artificial intelligence applications are ethical, compliant with regulations, and trusted by the public?* This question was investigated by considering the what the ethical, privacy and governance issues were when deploying generative artificial intelligence.

The paradigm for this research was interpretivism, which enabled the researchers to appreciate and identify the challenges of deploying generative AI in public service, as well as how an individual or group interprets the world in relation to the research issue. This study used an inductive research approach, utilizing a qualitative method, to investigate how public services can address governance, privacy, and ethics concerns, ensuring that their generative artificial intelligence (AI) applications are ethical, compliant with regulations, and trusted by the public. Data was collected through an online questionnaire comprising open-ended questions, which allowed for gathering in-depth insights from a targeted group of Government Information Technology Officers (GITO)/ Chief Information Officers (CIOs) in the public service. These meth-

ods yield comprehensive data that provide more significant insights into assessing governance, privacy, and ethical considerations.

The questionnaire was crafted with open-ended questions aimed at exploring the views on how governance, privacy, and ethics issues can be addressed to ensure the ethical and regulatory-compliant use of generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) applications. The participants were selected based on their leadership roles and direct involvement in digital transformation and AI deployment within their departments. The online format facilitated efficient distribution and allowed respondents the flexibility to provide thoughtful, detailed responses at their convenience. This approach facilitates the collection of rich, qualitative data, providing valuable insights into the strategies and challenges of building public trust and ensuring the responsible adoption of Gen AI in public service.

The questionnaire was sent to the 66 members of the Government Information Technology Officers Council (GITOC), and only 21 responded. The qualitative responses obtained from the provided online questionnaire link were coded and analyzed using Braun and Clarke's [23] six recursive phases of Thematic Analysis (TA), because of its versatility in defining, analyzing, and interpreting qualitative data patterns of meaning. The steps included: (1) becoming familiar with the data by repeated reading of the responses; (2) generating the initial codes by the systematic labelling of meaningful aspects of the data; (3) seeking themes by clustering related codes; (4) examining themes in order to ensure coherence and separability; (5) specifying and labelling the themes in order to encapsulate the essence of each pattern; and (6) generating the conclusive analytic narrative with supporting illustrative quotes.

4 Findings and Analysis

These findings reveal several overarching themes and sub-themes that encompass issues of governance, ethics, and privacy related to the public sector's use of generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI). Insights gathered from government technology officers/chief information officers reveal the complex impact of Gen AI. The findings reveal both positive and negative implications, particularly regarding governance structures, ethics, risks of privacy loss, and responsible use. In particular, key findings reveal varying perceptions of regulatory issues, ethics, and privacy concerns associated with Gen AI innovations. Specifically, while Gen AI promises greater efficiency and innovation in public services, it also creates significant issues, such as loss of privacy in data, bias in algorithms, and an elevated scope of AI decision-making transparency. The findings indicate that balancing the challenges of gains from Gen AI utilization with enhanced governance and ethical guidelines is essential for public services.

4.1 Governance

Concerns of governance that dictate the deployment of generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) in the public service are paramount regarding grasping both the challenges and opportunities of its successful deployment. In this research, an online

questionnaire was distributed to the Government Information Technology Officer to explore governance dilemmas related to the deployment of Gen AI. The experiences of such respondents shed light on these dynamics, particularly regarding the need for clear governance structures, overcoming infrastructural limitations, and countering the risks associated with Gen AI technology integration due to a lack of oversight. The subsequent sections outline key observations related to these governance concerns.

4.1.1 Absence of Policy and Frameworks

One significant governance issue raised by participants was the lack of policies and guidelines regulating the use of generative AI in the public service. Various participants expressed concern about the lack of clear guidelines to manage the ethical and legal uses of Gen AI technologies. The lack of a codified policy creates confusion in public service, as the deployment of Gen AI is made through decisions in the absence of predefined norms and oversight. The scenario may lead to divergent practices and increased risks of ethical issues. Furthermore, ambiguity in predefined governance structures also makes it harder for departments to take responsibility for the implications of AI-produced decisions, thereby thwarting efforts to encourage the responsible use of artificial intelligence. Participant 1 noted, *There is no unified policy for AI deployment in the public sector, leaving departments to operate without clear guidelines or regulations (P1)*. Another participant echoed this sentiment, stating, *Without a standardized framework, we are left to navigate the complexities of Gen AI on our own, which leads to inconsistent practices across different government departments (P3)*.

4.1.2 Infrastructure and Capacity Constraints

One of the key governance concerns raised by respondents included constraints in existing infrastructure and the capability to handle efficient management and integration of Gen AI technology. Different respondents mentioned that it is challenging to deploy Gen AI in public services that lack proper technological support or qualified staff. The limitations discourage entities at the departmental level from fully reaping the advantages of Gen AI systems, as ageing hardware, limited software capabilities, and underperforming networking hardware hinder efficient implementation and integration mechanisms. Moreover, inadequately skilled individuals with expert-level Gen AI and data management knowledge exacerbate such issues, further hindering an organization's ability to track, sustain, and optimise Gen AI deployments optimally. Such infrastructure and capability shortages could cause significant delays, loss of efficiency, and increased managerial risks, further underscoring the imperative of specialized investments in both technological assets and human capital to handle efficient Gen AI integration in the public services. Participant 4 explained, *Public sector organizations often have outdated infrastructure that is not equipped to handle the demands of Gen AI technologies. This makes integration difficult and costly (P4)*.

Participant 6 also raised concerns about the skills gap, stating, *We simply don't have enough people with the right skills to manage Gen AI systems. There's a shortage of trained professionals who can effectively integrate and monitor these technologies (P6).*

4.1.3 Rapid Adoption Without Governance

The rapid deployment of Gen AI solutions in the public sector, without proper governance and regulatory oversight, was another critical issue highlighted by respondents. Several respondents also expressed concerns that the widespread deployment of Gen AI systems has occurred before adequate governance structures are in place, which are essential for the responsible development and deployment of Gen AI solutions. The deployments usually take place at a rapid pace, resulting in a disjointed approach to implementation, whereby AI solutions are being implemented in parts of the organisation without due coordination, oversight, or compliance with established practices. Inadequate governance increases the risks of ethical transgressions, non-compliance with the law, and divergent outcomes in public service. The respondents noted that, while efficiency and innovation are key motivators in AI adoption, such reckless deployment works against accountability by favouring deployment at the expense of establishing proper oversight structures, risking a loss of public confidence in Gen AI systems. Participant 8 noted, *There's a rush to implement AI, but without sufficient thought given to the regulatory measures needed to ensure ethical and responsible use (P8).* Participant 10 further emphasized, *While the adoption of Gen AI in public service is crucial for improving efficiency, we cannot afford to skip the governance stage. Without proper oversight, we risk the uncontrolled use of AI technologies that could harm public trust (P10).*

4.2 Ethical challenges

This research has been of key concern regarding the ethical considerations of using generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) in public services. Government Information Technology Officer were specifically asked to complete the questions, to gather insights into ethical issues related to implementing generative AI technologies in public services. The views of such professionals regarding ethical challenges are listed in the following sections.

4.2.1 Bias and Discrimination

One of the key moral issues that has emerged regarding the use of generative AI (Gen AI) in public services is the issue of AI model bias and its potential for discrimination in decision-making. Several participants expressed concern about the potential of generative AI systems to inadvertently reinforce existing societal biases, particularly when training data is based on historical inequalities or lacks representation for diverse communities. This means that generative AI models can reinforce stereotypes, bias decision-making, or be biased against certain groups, thereby damaging the ethi-

cal value of public service use. The participants also pointed out that such bias could damage public confidence in generative AI systems, especially when such systems are making decisions of substantial social, economic, or legal consequence. Mitigating such bias is essential for the equitable implementation of generative AI technology, preventing the reinforcement of discrimination or inequality. According to Participant 1, *Bias in training data means that Gen AI is likely to replicate these biases in its outputs, leading to decisions that unfairly disadvantage certain groups (P1)*. Similarly, Participant 3 noted, *AI models trained on historical data tend to reinforce the biases already present in society, especially when the datasets are not diverse or balanced (P3)*.

4.2.2 Deepfakes and Misinformation

One of the key moral concerns raised by respondents was the potential for generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) to create damaging content, such as deepfakes and false information. Respondents expressed concern about the increased use of Gen AI in creating completely fabricated content that is presented convincingly and authentically, which can be abused negatively, such as to influence public opinion, slander individuals, or spread misinformation. This is of the highest concern in fields such as government, politics, media, and public relations, as spreading inaccurate information can have severe impacts. Most respondents felt that the possibility of abuse of this kind makes it even more critical that good governance structures be in place to govern how Gen AI is used, such that this kind of fraudulent content should not be created, let alone distributed, in a manner that harms people. They called for clear guidelines to sufficiently address the risks this technology poses, so that it is not exploited to subvert public confidence, deceive people, or interfere with democratic processes. They also defined, *Deepfakes pose a serious threat, especially in the political realm, where they can manipulate public opinion (P6)*. Participant 2 also highlighted the ethical dilemma of using Gen AI to generate content that could mislead or deceive the public. *Gen AI can be used to create fabricated news reports or manipulate public perceptions, which undermines trust in media and democratic institutions (P2)*.

4.2.3 Accountability and Transparency

A recurring ethical concern raised by participants was the need for greater accountability and transparency in decision-making by generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) systems. Participants highlighted that, without explicit measures to track and justify AI-based decisions, there is a strong risk of undermining public trust and eroding confidence in technology, especially when such decisions directly affect people's lives. Transparency in the AI process was deemed necessary so that Gen AI outputs can be clearly understood, scrutinized, and challenged when necessary. Accountability mechanisms, in terms of defined roles, responsibilities, and oversight procedures, also emerged as critically important for identifying mistakes, preventing misuse, and upholding ethics. The combination of transparency and accountability enables public

services to utilize Gen AI responsibly, demonstrating compliance with laws, ethics, and societal expectations while minimizing the potential for harm and adverse side effects. Participant 4 emphasized, *making AI decisions explainable and accountable, particularly in sensitive areas like law enforcement and healthcare (P4)*. Participant 9 raised an important point regarding public trust in AI systems, *If the public doesn't understand how an AI system arrived at a particular decision, it undermines the legitimacy of the entire system (P9)*.

4.2.4 Ethical Guidelines and Culture

Establishing broad ethical guidelines and fostering a responsible culture within the public service are seen as essential for the proper use of generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) technologies. The participants highlighted that guidelines alone are not enough without embedding ethical principles into daily routines, decision-making processes, and organisational values. A strong ethical culture ensures that Gen AI technologies are utilized in ways that align with public expectations, legal requirements, and professional standards, while also promoting accountability and transparency. The participants emphasized that ongoing and comprehensive training, awareness campaigns, and leadership commitment are essential to fostering such a culture, thereby reducing the risks of bias, misuse, and harm caused by ignorance. Participant 10 called for "clear ethical guidelines that define what is acceptable and what is not in deployment of Gen AI." (P10). Likewise, Participant 6 mentioned, *Without an established code of ethics, there's a risk that AI will be deployed in ways that could harm society or violate individual rights (P6)*.

4.3 Privacy Risks and Data Protection

Risks to privacy in generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) applications in the public service emerged as a key concern in this research. Respondents highlight several major concerns regarding privacy in relation to Gen AI deployment, including data management and ownership, data security and anonymization measures, and surveillance risks associated with AI-based systems.

4.3.1 Data Handling and Ownership

One of the major issues raised by participants regarding privacy protection in the use of generative artificial intelligence (Gen AI) systems is the management and ownership of personal data. Different participants emphasized the importance of transparent data ownership rights and consent procedures when using personal data in the development of Gen AI models. They noted that without clear ownership and consent protocols, individuals' personal data could be exploited or shared without their knowledge, potentially leading to ethical and legal violations. Additionally, participants indicated that confusion over data ownership exacerbates accountability issues because it makes it more difficult to determine who should be responsible for managing, securing, or correcting personal data in AI systems. Addressing these concerns carefully is crucial for both maintaining public trust and ensuring the responsible deployment of Gen AI

technologies in the public sector. Participant 1 expressed concern, stating, *Users need to have full control over their data, and it should be clear how their information is being used in the training of Gen AI systems (P1).*

4.3.2 Data Security and Anonymization

One of the primary concerns about privacy raised by participants was the need to implement robust data security and data anonymization methods to minimize data exposure risks. Most participants raised concerns about the data security risks associated with data exposure and emphasized the importance of safe data handling practices. They pointed out that Gen AI systems handle enormous amounts of personal and confidential data, leaving them at exceptionally high risks of unauthorized access, cyberattack, or accidental exposure. The respondents reported that, without proper protection measures, public service institutions pose a threat to personal privacy, thereby placing people at further risk and diminishing trust in Gen AI technology. The need to adopt safe data storage practices, coupled with data encryption and data anonymization, has been regarded as one of the significant measures in combating personal data abuse, while concurrently combating both legal and ethical issues. Participant 4 pointed out, *With the vast amounts of data Gen AI systems require, ensuring that this data is securely stored and not exposed to unauthorized access is essential (P4).* Similarly, Participant 9 raised the issue of potential data leaks, saying, *If data used to train AI models is not adequately secured, it could lead to significant breaches of privacy, particularly when sensitive personal information is involved (P9).*

4.3.3 Surveillance and Monitoring Risks

The utilization of Gen AI systems in surveillance activities raised significant concerns regarding privacy among participants. Several participants noted potential misuses of personal data harvested by Gen AI based surveillance systems, such as unauthorized surveillance, bulk harvesting of data, and potential exploitation of such data in a manner that contravenes individuals' rights. The participants noted that the lack of visible regulatory control, as well as the absence of clear ethical guidelines, facilitates such potential misuses, especially when these systems are used in sensitive public sector environments. The concerns over AI-based surveillance also include a loss of transparency and accountability, which makes it harder to ensure that such data is handled in a manner that ensures proper security. Participant 5 noted, with Participant 5 noting, *AI-powered surveillance systems can easily cross ethical boundaries if not carefully regulated, especially if the data collected is used for purposes other than what it was originally intended for (P5).*

5 Guidelines

The analysis of the empirical data revealed several recurring themes related to governance, privacy, and ethical considerations associated with the use of generative artificial intelligence in government. Participants emphasized the need for structured oversight, responsible data management, and mechanisms to ensure transparency and accountability when deploying AI technologies in public services. These themes highlight the complexity of adopting generative AI within government environments where public trust, legal compliance, and ethical responsibility are central. Based on these findings, a set of practical guidelines was developed to support the responsible adoption and implementation of generative AI in government institutions. The guidelines reflect the key concerns and insights expressed by respondents and provide direction for policymakers and public sector organisations seeking to balance technological innovation with governance, privacy protection, and ethical accountability.

1. Establish a formal generative AI governance framework: Every government department should adopt a clear framework that sets out approved uses, prohibited uses, review processes, and compliance requirements for generative AI. This addresses the article's concern that weak policy direction leads to inconsistent practices, weak oversight, and greater ethical and legal risk.
2. Define accountability and oversight roles: Specific officials or committees should be responsible for authorizing, monitoring, and reviewing AI systems in public service. Clear accountability strengthens governance because it makes it easier to identify who must answer for errors, misuse, harmful outputs, or unlawful data practices.
3. Do not deploy AI before governance is in place: Generative AI should not be rolled out simply because it promises efficiency or innovation. The article shows that rapid adoption without proper oversight increases the risk of non-compliance, weak controls, and loss of public trust.
4. Protect personal data through clear ownership and consent rules: Government institutions should define who owns the data, who can access it, and how consent is obtained when personal information is used. This is essential because unclear data ownership creates privacy violations and weakens accountability for how citizens' information is handled.
5. Apply strong data security and anonymization measures: Sensitive data used in generative AI systems should be encrypted, securely stored, access-controlled, and anonymized where possible. These controls reduce the risk of breaches, unlawful exposure, and misuse of confidential public information.
6. Test for bias and discrimination before and during use: AI systems should be evaluated for biased outputs, unfair treatment, and unequal impacts on different social groups. This is critical in government because biased models can reproduce historical inequality and undermine fairness in public decision making.
7. Require transparency and explainability: Citizens and officials should be able to understand how an AI system produced a recommendation, response, or decision. Transparency supports ethical use because decisions that affect people's lives must be open to scrutiny, explanation, and challenge.

8. Keep a human in the loop for high impact decisions: Generative AI should support public officials, not replace human judgement in sensitive areas such as healthcare, law enforcement, and social services. Human oversight helps prevent harmful automated decisions and reinforces accountability when outcomes affect rights and livelihoods.
 9. Set rules to prevent misinformation, deepfakes, and harmful content: Government use of generative AI should include controls to detect, flag, and prevent false, misleading, or manipulated content. This is necessary because the article highlights the ethical danger of deepfakes and fabricated information in shaping public opinion and weakening democratic trust.
 10. Build an ethical culture through training and stakeholder engagement: Officials should receive ongoing training on governance, privacy, ethics, and responsible AI use, while citizens and stakeholders should be included in discussions on adoption. The article makes clear that responsible implementation depends not only on rules, but also on awareness, public participation, and a culture of ethical conduct.
- The guidelines provide practical direction for government institutions seeking to adopt generative AI in a responsible and accountable manner. Adherence to these principles supports effective governance, protects citizen privacy, and promotes ethical use of AI technologies in the delivery of public services.

6 Conclusion

Generative Artificial Intelligence presents significant opportunities for governments to improve efficiency, innovation, and the delivery of public services. The findings of this study show that while the technology offers clear benefits for decision support, service optimisation, and knowledge generation, its adoption also introduces complex governance, privacy, and ethical challenges. Concerns related to data protection, algorithmic bias, transparency of AI outputs, and the absence of comprehensive regulatory structures highlight the need for a cautious and structured approach to implementation. The perspectives gathered from government technology professionals indicate that responsible adoption requires stronger oversight mechanisms and clearly defined policies that guide the use of generative AI within public institutions.

The research emphasizes that effective governance frameworks, ethical standards, and clear regulatory guidance are essential to ensure that generative AI is implemented in a manner that protects citizens and maintains public trust. Government institutions must prioritise transparency, accountability, and responsible data management when integrating these technologies into public sector environments. In addition, ongoing training, stakeholder engagement, and continuous monitoring of AI systems will support responsible use and reduce potential risks.

References

- [1] A. Taeihagh, M. Ramesh, and M. Howlett, "Assessing the regulatory challenges of emerging disruptive technologies," *Regul. Gov.*, vol. 15, no. 4, pp. 1009–1019, 2021.

- [2] H. Aryfiyanto and A. Alamsyah, "Public Service with Generative AI: Exploring Features and Applications," in 2024 7th International Conference of Computer and Informatics Engineering (IC2IE), Bali, Indonesia: IEEE, Sep. 2024, pp. 1–7. doi: 10.1109/IC2IE63342.2024.10747963.
- [3] DCDT, "AI National Government Summit Discussion Document. Department of Communications and Digital Technologies."
- [4] J. Merilehto, "On Generative Artificial Intelligence: Open-Source is the Way," 2024.
- [5] DPSA and Public Service and Administration, DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION STRATEGY OF THE PUBLIC SERVICES. 2024.
- [6] Presidency, SOUTH AFRICA'S ROADMAP FOR THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF GOVERNMENT. [Online]. Available: https://stateofthenation.gov.za/assets/downloads/South_Africa_Roadmap_for_the_Digital_Transformation.pdf
- [7] J. Bright, F. E. Enock, S. Esnaashari, J. Francis, Y. Hashem, and D. Morgan, "Generative AI is already widespread in the public sector," ArXiv Prepr. ArXiv240101291, 2024.
- [8] M. Wessel, M. Adam, A. Benlian, and F. Thies, "Generative AI and its transformative value for digital platforms," J. Manag. Inf. Syst., 2023.
- [9] N. Rane, "ChatGPT and Similar Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) for Smart Industry: Role, Challenges and Opportunities for Industry 4.0, Industry 5.0 and Society 5.0," SSRN Electron. J., 2023, doi: 10.2139/ssrn.4603234.
- [10] K.-B. Ooi et al., "The potential of generative artificial intelligence across disciplines: Perspectives and future directions," J. Comput. Inf. Syst., pp. 1–32, 2023.
- [11] M. Zhou, V. Abhishek, T. Derdenger, J. Kim, and K. Srinivasan, "Bias in Generative AI," ArXiv Prepr. ArXiv240302726, 2024.
- [12] M. Yahaya, A. Umagba, S. Obeta, and T. Maruyama, "Critical Evaluation of the Future Role of Artificial Intelligence in Business and Society," J. Artif. Intell. Mach. Learn. Data Sci., vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 21–29, 2023, doi: 10.51219/JAIMLD/Moshood-Yahaya/03.
- [13] M. T. Baldassarre, D. Caivano, B. Fernandez Nieto, D. Gigante, and A. Ragone, "The social impact of generative ai: An analysis on chatgpt," presented at the Proceedings of the 2023 ACM Conference on Information Technology for Social Good, 2023, pp. 363–373.
- [14] Y. Chinthapatla, "Safeguarding the Future: Nurturing Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence Ecosystems and the Role of Legal Frameworks," Int. J. Sci. Res. Sci. Eng. Technol., vol. 12, no. 04, 2024.
- [15] V. D. Kirova, C. S. Ku, J. R. Laracy, and T. J. Marlowe, "The Ethics of Artificial Intelligence in the Era of Generative AI," J. Syst. Cybern. Inform., vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 42–50, 2023, doi: 10.54808/jsci.21.04.42.
- [16] S. Fukuda-Parr and E. Gibbons, "Emerging consensus on 'ethical AI': Human rights critique of stakeholder guidelines," Glob. Policy, vol. 12, pp. 32–44, 2021.
- [17] D. Mhlanga, "Generative AI for Emerging Researchers: The Promises, Ethics, and Risks," Ethics Risks Febr. 24 2024, 2024.
- [18] D. Oniani et al., "From military to healthcare: Adopting and expanding ethical principles for generative artificial intelligence," ArXiv Prepr. ArXiv230802448, 2023.
- [19] R. Rousi et al., "Business and ethical concerns in domestic Conversational Generative AI-empowered multi-robot systems," presented at the International Conference on Software Business, Springer Nature Switzerland Cham, 2023, pp. 173–189.

- [20] D. Korobenko, A. Nikiforova, and R. Sharma, "Towards a Privacy and Security-Aware Framework for Ethical AI: Guiding the Development and Assessment of AI Systems," 25th Annu. Int. Conf. Digit. Gov. Res., 2024.
- [21] S. Thorne, "Understanding the Interplay between Trust, Reliability, and Human Factors in the Age of Generative AI," *Int. J. Simul. Syst. Sci. Technol.*, 2023.
- [22] Y. Wang, Y. Pan, M. Yan, Z. Su, and T. H. Luan, "A survey on ChatGPT: AI-generated contents, challenges, and solutions," *IEEE Open J. Comput. Soc.*, 2023.
- [23] S. K. Ahmed et al., "Using thematic analysis in qualitative research," *J. Med. Surg. Public Health*, vol. 6, p. 100198, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.glmedi.2025.100198.